

INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS AND TEACHER PERFORMANCE: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators and Teacher Performance: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of instructional leadership practices of school administrators to teacher performance. Correlational method or Pearson r was used and validated through survey questionnaire to measure the level of Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators and Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) to validate the performance of 150 teachers of Trento District, Poblacion, Trento Agusan del Sur. The level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators was measured in terms of supervision, time management and information communication technology competence in operationalization. The result showed the instructional leadership practices has no associated correlation between the variables teachers' performance rating. Teachers' performance has no relatively association between Instructional leadership practices. Teachers performed their duties and responsibilities as an educator according to their commitment, dedication and passion. With that profound accountability being an educationalist, whose desire is to potentially produce holistic individuals, the absence of instructional leadership practices would not be an obstacle towards teachers' highly proficient performance. The results indicated that teachers showed better performance if the intensity of commitment was better. Thus, when teachers are incredibly motivated, the success of their work becomes significant. On the other hand, to become efficient and effective school administrators, school heads must perform five outstanding leadership practices providing the foundation for organizational performance by suggesting what attitudes and behaviors school officials need to accomplish to become successful leaders. It is recommended that the Department of Education supports enhancement seminar workshop to improve school head instructional leadership practices as to supervision, time management and information and communication technology competence in operationalization. The conduct of orientation and seminar workshops that would inspire teachers' commitment to increase their dedication to teaching and teamwork.

Keywords: *instructional leadership practices, teachers' performance, correlational study*

Introduction

Instructional Leadership provides significant role towards teachers' performance in the delivery of quality education. School Administrator, as the prime mover of this endeavor has been expected to engage in instructional leadership practices to bring about the efficiency and effectiveness of teachers' performance. Moreover, in order to provide high quality teaching and learning, school administrators are responsible for overseeing the instructional leadership practices as to supervision, time management and information and communication technology competence in operationalization. These practices must be maximized to promote the achievement of educational goals and objectives. Onuma (2016) expressed that the school administrator's main responsibilities are to demonstrate excellent instructional leadership techniques for the successful accomplishment of predetermined school goals.

Moreover, in the United States' Department of Education, leadership determines the success and significance of an organization and is a key component of school improvement (Goolamally & Ahmad, 2014). Being the school manager, you have the power and opportunity to guide teachers and all school staff towards the goal of all educational institutions -- to help prepare students for life, make them productive citizens and ready to take their place in society.

Furthermore, World Bank 2018 studies have found that school leaders establish the culture and organization necessary for schools to provide quality teaching and therefore have an indirect, but important, effect on student learning. By providing effective guidance, training, and working conditions to teachers, school leaders create the best possible environment for learning (Jensen, Downing & Clark, 2017; UNESCO, 2019).

Additionally, Reffel & Whitworth (2002) as cited by Cabanas (2013) expressed that the ability to use computers, as a main ICT device nowadays, effectively has become an essential part of everyone's education. It offers various skills such as information and communication technology competence. Administrative work, stocking, facilities inventory and many others are now greatly done through specific computer program.

In the Municipality of Trento, Agusan del Sur there were 44 schools. Each school has a designated school administrators who is in-charge in managerial, instructional operations. However, some was appointed without following the 2019 DepEd Guidelines on the Selection, Promotion and Designation of School Heads under D.O. No. 85, s. 2003 in pursuance to RA 9155 on the basis of merit, competence, fitness and equality. Thus, different instructional leadership practices were being practiced. In this matter I want to conduct a study on how the instructional leadership practices affect the performance of the teachers.

Lastly, I encountered some teachers who expressed discontentment on the instructional leadership practices of their school administrators where they lamented on the practices relating to instructional supervision, time management, ICT competence in operationalization. There had been several studies on instructional leadership practices but were not being correlated to performance of teachers. This current study will attempt to investigate the influence of instructional leadership practices of instructional supervision, time management, school competence in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) operationalization to performance of elementary school teacher.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to investigate the instructional leadership practices of school administrators of Trento Municipality as to instructional supervision, time management and competence information and communication technology operationalization during the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to find out the answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators in terms of:
 - 1.1. instructional supervision;
 - 1.2. time management; and
 - 1.3. ICT competence in operationalization?
2. What is the level of performance of teachers based on the results in IPCRF?
 - 2.1. IPCRF Individual Performance Commitment Review Form
3. Is there a significant relationship between the instructional leadership practices of School Heads and to the performance of teachers?

Literature Review

The discussion was organized according to the following subsections: School administrators' instructional practices as to instructional supervision, time management, competence on information and communication technology and the influence of educational attainment and educational managerial trainings in managing a school.

Instructional practices as to instructional supervision. One of the most dominant variables that determines student learning outcomes is the teacher. Therefore, to improve student achievement, it is necessary to improve teacher competence. The main program to improve teacher competence is instructional supervision though its effectiveness is still questionable. To be able to effectively provide education, there is need to ensure that the educational system is reliable. Reliability in terms of educational system can only be enhanced through supervision (Peretomode, 2004).

As cited by Peretomode (2004) supervision can be divided into two categories. These are instructional and personnel supervision. Instructional supervision has been defined as a set of activities which are carried out with the purpose of making the teaching and learning purpose better for the learner. Personnel supervision on the other hand deals with the set of activities which are carried out by the supervisor with the basic aim of sensitizing, mobilizing and motivating staff in the school towards performing their duties optimally in terms of the achievement of the stated aims and objectives of the educational system.

Instructional supervision is that phase of school administration which focuses primarily upon the achievement of the appropriate expectations of educational system, cited in Peretomode (2004). It sees that those activities which are designed to improve instruction at all levels of the school enterprise and as behavior officially designed by the organization that directly affects teacher behavior in such a way to facilitate pupil learning and achieve the goals of the organization. It is basically concerned with supporting and assisting teachers to improve instructions through changing their behavior. The instructional supervisor does much than inspect. Instructional supervision is a service activity that exists to help teachers do their job better. According to Berman (2006) School Administrators, though not personally responsible for maintaining the school plant, cannot assume that the task will be carried out efficiently without some supervision on his/her part thus must be well supervised.

Conferring to Akinwumiju and Agabi (2008) instructional supervision as a collaborative effort involving a set of activities designed to improve the teaching and learning process. The purpose of supervision is not to find fault or to punish, but rather to work cooperatively with the teacher. Supervision as the element of the administrative process is concerned with efforts to guide the day-to-day activities of the work group by stimulating, directing and coordinating the workers and their efforts, cultivating good working personal relationships so that they all work towards a more efficient achievement of the task goal.

Also, highlighting the functional similarities states that supervision and inspection are administrative functions directed towards the efficient achievement of organizational goals. Their central purpose is to enhance productivity and both constitute tools for educational coordination. But the authors still find differences, thus: the words "supervision" and "inspection" are often used to mean the same but they are two different concepts in terms of job content and scope. Supervision is designed to achieve improvement in instruction, resolution of school constraints, maintenance of superordinate- subordinate cooperation, professionalism and autonomy of staff and achievement of intrinsic motivation while Inspection is carried out specifically to ensure that minimum standards are maintained in the basic activities of teaching and learning. This is with regards to content coverage, resource provision, maintenance of discipline and

keeping of statutory records and accounts. It also provides opportunities to access the challenges confronting the school and the level of success achieved in the pursuit of school goals. (Akinwumiju & Agabi, 2008).

Additionally, Nwagwu (2004) views supervision as one of the basic requirements of administration that concerns itself with the tactics of efficiency and effective management of human and material resources. It is a way to advise, guide, refresh, encourage, simulate, improve and oversee teachers with the hope of seeking their cooperation in order that they may be successful in the task of teaching and classroom management. Undoubtedly, the most important supervision and guidance in the school setting is that given by the head of the school (Mofareh, 2011). Further, the concept of direct supervision as a form of instructional supervision refers to all the measures by the school administrators to facilitate one-on-one feedback with teachers to enhance instruction and professional capacity (Glickman, Gordon & Ross-Gordon, 2009)

Educational supervision is a process to ascertain that the teachers carry out the task of teaching to an expected level according to the stipulated guidelines, which control the educational system. It is a way of persuading workers to desist from applying wrong methods and procedures in carrying out certain functions of their jobs. While Nwagwu (2004) lectured that inspection is seen as an instrument with which the political and administrative authorities maintain the necessary contact with the schools, teachers, pupils and the community and so ensure that the system is working satisfactorily. In this sense inspection is to be viewed as fulfilling a controlling, coordinating and communicating role as guardian of education standards. As mentioned by Wanzare (2011) Instructional supervision improves the quality of teachers and teaching, facilitates students' academic performance and provides the opportunity to monitor teachers' instructional work.

Lastly, Peretomode (2004) outlined activities that the skillful instructional supervisor can utilize to bring about desirable effect in teacher behavior for achieving teaching effectiveness. These includes, first, classroom observation which involves live observing of a teacher and analyzing his or her classroom practices, the teaching - learning process, teachers' personality, student-teacher interactions, lesson note and lesson presentation. All these are observed by the supervisor who is present as a witness. Second, Demonstration it involves the presentation of a prearranged series of events to a group for their view. This stimulates teachers' growth and group discussion.

Third, Teacher visitation his activity also called "intervisiting" or "reciprocal visitations" involves one teacher visiting and observing another teacher in action in another class within the same school (inter-class visitation) or in another school European Scientific Journal (inter-school visitation). This method enhances proficiency especially if the beginning or inexperienced teacher watches experienced teacher in action. Fourth, workshop this activity involves a small group of people temporarily formed to discuss a specific topic or work on a common problem and trying to find solutions to a specific problem in a face-to-face situation.

Fifth, Micro-teaching- it is a teaching situation which is scaled down in terms of time, class size and teaching complexity to allow the teacher focus on a selected teaching strategy. New skills are developed and old ones are refined. Usually, it involves a small group of 5-10 pupils where the teacher employs a particular skill within say ten minutes involving content and skill. Emphasis is on the issue of immediate feedback where the teacher is evaluated by the supervisor in form of replaying a recorded lesson or actual discussion (if it was not recorded). When corrections are made the teacher re-teaches the lesson to the same group or a different group for improvement. Sixth, Listening to tape, radio or recordings: This involves using sound recordings to present ideas to one or more listeners in such way as to help develop understanding or skills.

Also, the use of visual presentations through the media film, television, or video tape are increasingly important in the supervisory process. Seventh is Guided Practice: This supervision technique involves individualized or small group manipulative activities. It is an approach in which doing is emphasized rather than talking with practice activities arranged out of context. Lastly is Research: Research is the systematic and objective collection and analysis of data in order to find solutions to identified problems. Here the supervisor work with and through teachers to finding solutions to problems of teaching/learning that confronts them instead of dictating solutions to or autocratically setting educational problems relating to teaching and teachers.

Research shown that school administrators' direct supervision of teachers concerned with improvement of the conditions that surrounds learning, pupil growth and effective teacher role performance in the school system (Alemayehu, 2008). Focuses on identifying pedagogical challenges encountered by their teachers in their instructional delivery and providing them with need support to overcome them (Glanz, Shulman & Sullivan, 2007).

Also, it creates a platform for both teachers and school administrators to use their collective expertise in self-appraisal of teachers, to identify gaps in teacher skills, knowledge and competencies in order to provide the vital support needed for teachers' professional development.

Therefore, quality education can be actualized where the educational system is reliable and this reliability can only be achieved through both instructional and personnel supervision by the principals. The role of the principals is to facilitate the implementation of the various sets of instructional activities that will improve the teaching-learning situation in the input process - output framework without which the educational endeavors may be an exercise in futility.

As emphasized in the Journal of Education and Practice on The Impact of Instructional Supervision on Academic Performance of

Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria Usman, the impact of positive/negative remarks by supervisors on teacher's performance was significant. This implies that good comments by supervisors during the supervision process have a measurable bearing in improving the teacher performance in the teaching –learning process. The analysis established a significant relationship between supervisory climate and improved teachers' performance.

The findings further indicated that negative comments by supervisors have an adverse effect on teacher's performance. It reveals that, if teachers develop apathy, negative attitude towards the administrator or supervisor because of his/her harsh method of approach, his/her performance will be lowered and this will affect his performance in the instructional process especially when the supervisor is with him/her.

Instructional practices as to time management. Time management is the coordination of tasks and activities to maximize the effectiveness of an individual's efforts. Essentially, the purpose of time management is to enable people to get more and better work done in less time. It cannot be accumulated for future use and cannot be taken back once it is use (Mercanlioglu, 2010). Also, (Zeinuddine, 2018) defines time management as “ the optimum use of resources available to the school in achieving its goals the least effort, within the limits of available school hours”.

Elements of time management include organization, planning and scheduling to best take advantage of the time available. Time management techniques also take into account an individual's particular situation and their relevant capabilities and characteristics. Time management has been offered as “ a form of self-management with a clear emphasis on time in understanding what activities to do; how to do them more efficiently; what time should it be done and when is the correct time to the particular activity” (Savino, 2016, Alyami et al., 2021).

The importance of time management is in its ability to assign meaning to time, letting people make the most of their time. Good time management skills help employees deliver quality work and meet their goals effectively. It helps managers or school leaders to understand what employees are capable of and to set realistic goals. To optimally use the time available and that includes aspects of planning, goal setting, prioritizing goals and activities, communications and delegation' (Marquis, 2012; Finkelman, 2006; Ghiasy & et al., 2017)

However, poor time management skills cause employees to miss goals and deliver poor work, become overly stressed out and anxious, and run short of time. When time is used inefficiently, it has deleterious effects on employees, management and the organization. Time poverty is a result of poor or nonexistent time management. People find themselves in this state when they have too much to do and too little time to do it. Their personal lives suffer, and they feel increasingly overwhelmed with responsibilities and activities despite working hard. According to Akinyemi & Ajayi, “it seems that the main reason some school administrators face challenges in meeting deadline and curriculum goals is poor time management” (Akinyemi & Ajayi, 2020)

Moreover, time management requires active decisions about what a person wants to do. Without time management, individuals continually react to external stimuli and lose a sense of control over their work and lives. All work takes time, but some tasks are more valuable than others. Reallocating time to higher-value work improves both productivity and work-life balance. Good time management creates a healthier workplace overall. School Administrators time management strategies would help them have effective administration (Akomolafe, 2013; Naparan & Tulod, 2021). Also, administrative job satisfaction increases (Hussain et al., 2019)

As stated by Dr. John Murray in his article Time Management Tips for School Leaders - Part I that the complexity and variety of competing responsibilities associated with being a school principal are rivaled by a few other occupations. Managing everything can seem overwhelming, with principals citing time management as one of the top three challenges of their jobs (Grissom, Loeb, & Mitani, 2015). Principals often find their time eaten up by necessary but less important tasks and activities.

Additionally, Ben Lutkevich Technical Features Writer, TechTarget emphasized in his article some challenges of time management by Mallary Tytel, categorizes barriers to effective time management as either internal or external.

Internal barriers are ones that come from the individual and are within the individual's control. They include factors such as the following: Lack of self-control. An individual who lacks self-control is prone to distraction and might miss goals because of this. Procrastination. People put off tasks until they feel pressured to complete them. This is a reactive behavior. Lack of motivation. An individual might not see the reason for completing something, choosing to do something else and setting other goals.

Anxiety. Individuals experiencing stress likely find it harder to focus and be decisive. People pleasing. A person who is preoccupied with pleasing everyone inevitably fails because other people have conflicting needs; the individual will spread themselves too thin trying to please them all. Multitasking. Trying to do too many things at once, or multitasking, can mean failing at all of them. These internal factors relate to an individual's habits, behaviors and actions. Though the behaviors might be unconscious or ingrained, an individual has the power to moderate their behaviors and change the way they use time.

It was emphasized by Mallary Tytel that external barriers are factors that come from outside the individual. They include factors such as the following: Workload. An individual can end up with more work than they can handle. Job constraints. The job or workplace might keep the individual from reaching their goals. Lack of corporate resources. A company might not provide the resources employees need to complete their jobs. For example, it might be a remote-only position, but the company doesn't provide collaboration

tools for team members to work well remotely. Distractions. External life factors, such as a family emergency or a global pandemic, might disrupt an individual's ability to manage their time effectively. Basic time wasters such as social media can also be a time suck.

External barriers, unlike internal ones, are not within the individual's control. They come from the outside environment. However, the individual can control how they react to these barriers. Moreover, there were time management tips and techniques presented for achieving better time management like keeping a journal of activities for a week to identify the times of day that are likely to be most productive, use that information to guide scheduling tasks, take time at the start of each workday to make a to-do list of measurable goals and methods of reaching them, schedule daily tasks according to priority and include unscheduled time in the day, manage your communication availability, assume periodic interruptions will happen and add time to specific tasks to allow for them and manage your workload. Don't agree to more work than you can comfortably do and discuss unreasonable demands with management. As a school administrator, time is the scarcest resource (Olaniyan, 2008), and unless it is managed, nothing else can be managed (Mitani, 2013).

Persistence of competing demands at school may result in various professional and personal problems for principals. Time management and organizational problems can raise stress levels, especially when school administrators must balance their work and family responsibilities (Fields & Egley, 2005; Hausman et al., 2002). The time for school administrators is a resource, to be used productively. Good use of time requires self-understanding, personal commitment, discipline, organization, and planning." The significance of school principals managing time is well researched and it is generally agreed that principals frequently experience time management difficulties in their managerial and administrative duties (Lyons). Even, most successful school principals face time management issues in school (Altun, 2011). Managing time efficiently increases one's productivity, limits burnout, promotes advancement, and improves both personal and professional satisfaction (Gordon & Borkan, 2014).

For the leadership to be effective timely decisions are important, demonstrated through the association between time use and school outcome of school principals (Grissom et al., 2013; Horng, Klasik & Loeb, 2010).

However, strategies and practices for improving time management aspects of school principals are lacking in the current educational literature and it is considered as an obstacle in the completion of work (Kennedy, 2002; Liu et al., 2009). School principals get frustrated in completing paperwork, attending meetings, responding to emails and phone messages, and striving to meet unrealistic deadlines (Barnet et al., 2012).

Many professions place high demands on a person's efficient use of time (Kearns & Gardiner, 2007). As Britton & Glynn put it, "intellectually productive people usually have more things that they would like to do, or need to do, than they have time." This description can be applied to the work of most principals of schools, having time constraints for running school affairs, coordinating instructional programs, maintaining relations amongst staff members, and so forth (Barnett et al., 2012; Horng et al., 2010).

In such professions, becoming more effective means discovering strategies to achieve more in a specified period of time. Efficient time management is one of the important strategies for the achievement of goals. Claessens et al., (2007) suggest that time management means those "behaviors that aim at achieving an efficient use of time while performing certain goal-directed activities." Literature recommends effective time management abilities – which include the ability to identify priorities, check one's progress, set achievable goals, and remaining organized (Claessens et al., 2007) Time has not been ever truly defined by anybody. Time is indefinable and invisible. Time is money – a limited, valuable resource – and cannot be stored in the bank like money. It cannot be increased by working hard. People cannot buy it, cannot stop, cannot save, steal, borrow or change it in any way.

Time is irreversible, indispensable, irreplaceable and inelastic. Literature on time management suggests that there are hundreds and thousands of self-help books which can be fruitful for the individuals to manage and utilize their time through practices like writing "to-do" lists, prioritizing the tasks on the basis of their importance, planning ahead and effectively and efficiently managing meetings and keeping away from bad habits like interruption and procrastination.

However, despite recommending excellent time management skills in organizations and workspaces, it appears that a small number of researches have truly documented the empirical soundness of essential time management practices (Horng et al., 2010) found that school principals spent just about 20% of their time in transition between everyday jobs. Principals spent 54% of their time in the school office and another 9% in the main school building. Moreover, 40% time of the principals was spent in observing teachers and students in playgrounds, classrooms, and in halls. On average, the principals spent only 8% of the school time in classroom teaching. Principals spent even a smaller amount of time, just about 4%, off the school entirely.

To become efficient school administrator there were strategies which can increase time management skills. It may include setting attainable goals, prioritizing tasks, involving a team, maximizing planning, problem-solving difficulties, and skillful handling of possible interruptions (Chase et al., 2013). Continuous evaluation of the effectiveness of time management practices allows school principals to identify areas of productivity and judging progress. Time management strategies also highlight the importance of time management and facilitate teaching-learning process, in achieving educational aims, goals and objectives.

Mullins (2005) suggests that "whatever, the attributes or qualities of successful managers are, or the qualities of subordinate staff are, one essential underlying criterion is the effective use of time." Schriber and Gutek listed nine significant temporal dimensions primarily

facilitated by time management competencies of personnel and their associated personality dimensions (procrastination avoidance; punctuality; temporal prioritizing of tasks; awareness of time uses and planning; staying on schedule; accurate allocation of time; meeting deadlines; autonomy of time use; and synchronization and coordination).

While, LeBoeuf (2003) has given a list of fifteen time wasting tasks by executives in fourteen countries. These include lack of objectives; priorities and deadlines; telephone interruptions; scheduled and unscheduled meetings; drop-in visitors; cluttered desk and personal disorganization; crises; unsuccessful delegation; unclear communication and instruction; attempting too much at once and estimating time unrealistically; inadequate or inaccurate or delayed information; confused responsibility and authority; indecision and procrastination; lack of self-discipline; and leaving tasks unfinished. Previous research and many books propose that principals can utilize time efficiently and effectively by setting long-term and short-term goals, keeping time logs, preparing 'to-do' lists, organizing one's workspace, scheduling and prioritizing tasks (Claessens et al., 2007).

On the other hand, Kaufman (2004) asserts that constantly late individuals cannot manage their time and routine appropriately and recommends that proper and appropriate planning is the main asset of the leader. Features that are directly related to efficient time management include good organization, having good filing system and time schedules and setting up a practice of study (Swart, Lombard, & Jager, 2010).

Though, schedules necessitate prioritizing (Mancini, 2003) and setting aside under continuous supervision, avoiding lapses and omissions (Bittel). McCuen argues that scheduling is one practice specified for managing time, through which procrastination can be avoided. A 'time planner' or schedule needs preparing according to priority, which may be in the form of a daily 'to-do list' or a checklist of what still desires to be completed (Swart et al., 2010).

One of the important dimensions to good organization is effective planning (Tracy, 2004) and a well-documented schedule (Swart et al., 2010). Tracy (2014) suggests a series of techniques for managing time: making written plans, creating daily "to-do" list, setting clear priorities, staying on track, determining key result areas, delegating power and authority to others, concentrating on work, overcoming procrastination, controlling interruptions, managing the telephone and conducting effective meetings. Gordon & Borkan (2014) have mentioned that effective time management approaches can be classified into four principles. These are long-term and short-term goals, planning and organizing activities, minimizing time wasters and selecting priorities among competing responsibilities.

There were four identified main behaviors of highly effective people on the basis of their experiences and courses conducted in the time management field by Kearns & Gardiner (2007). These include, planning and prioritizing tasks, clarity of purpose in work, avoiding interruptions and distractions and being organized. As an effective time management tool, Tracy (2004) also suggests employing a filing system. It is imperative for school principals to determine for work the time of day in which their energy levels, alertness and productiveness are at peak (Mancini, 2003; Tracy, 2004). Time management training can lead to effective and efficient use of time management behaviors, leading to more positive results. Principals must also consider structural complexity of the school and its size when seeking to deploy their educational expertise into practice (see Hallinger & Murphy, 2013)

Instructional practices as to competence on information and communication technology. School administrators is a key determinant for the realization of desired outcomes and success in both public and private schools hence is seen as critical by all stakeholders. Gray & Smith (2007) observed that twenty-first century school head faces numerous challenges emanating from the technology. Based on the experience of the researcher, there are so many adjustments that needs to encounter to face these challenges. It has been a complicated situation to continuously learn and relearn especially the computer skills that has been very necessary in doing a lot tasks. The challenge on making computer-generated reports, instructional materials and other tasks is seen to be very coercive.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are increasingly used and viewed as important in all spheres of operation including education. These require effective and dynamic school administrator. Hence, the researcher observed that most of the school administrators has low interest about engaging in the technology. As presented by Camacho & Pintor (2011), lack of initiatives of school administrator poses a problem in institutionalizing information and communication technology in the school. It is a fact in the district of Trento that majority of the school administrators seem to have very low interest in providing ICT facilities. The focus of their initiatives are usually physical facilities. This can be attributed to the lack of knowledge of school administrators on the use of technology.

Information is the basis of management, planning and evaluation of an education system. In relation to this, Martinet (2013) stated that technology is the key player in this modern-day information system management. During the education management process, the education management information system (EMIS) should inform the different actors and partners on the state of the sector, its internal and external efficiency, its pedagogical and institutional operation, its performance, shortcomings and needs. A solid information system should not only aim to collect, store data and process information but help in the formulation of education policies, their management and their evaluation.

School administrator with a not so organized system and poor technological facilities experience problems on lack of equipment, facilities and new technology. The difficulty of carrying out the duties and functions is very noticeable.

Likewise, Sharma (2012) cited that MIS can help in many ways the field of education if integrated with technology. This can help store student related information which facilitate decision making for taking routine decisions related to students' development and progress in the class. This further helps in planning their placement activity better and also making its footprint on managing alumni in long run, and much more. It also helps in managing human resources, the experts and overall knowledge management in the organization. There are many other areas in education that could be handled better with the help of MIS like research and consultancy work, infrastructure, corporate liasoning, conferences, journals etc.

Any collaborative environment that uses computer systems shall have information that has to be stored, processed, shared, exchanged and disseminated. Moses Yiga (2012) discussed that MIS (Management Information Systems) supports computer supported collaborative environments in the sense that any meaningful collaborative systems should have involve/engage management of Information in a computer environment. Hence, this information/data should be managed. Some examples are the data bases in any electronic form. Thus, MIS certainly should assist computer supported collaborative environments in any area of knowledge.

Many important changes have occurred in the last few years in the education systems which will require teachers and school leaders to upgrade and refine their technology skills (Adu, 2013). Some of these changes are due to changes in government policies related to the use of ICT in schools while others are due to developments in state-of-the-art pedagogical practices as technology flows faster into the schools. Many school leaders are facing a range of difficult system management issues. Also, many educational policies in DepEd influence the development of ICT for operational purposes.

Gibson (2002) stated that school leaders have to focus their energies on ten technology categories: existing practice, planning, curriculum, resources, staff issues, communications, support, obstacles, staff development and implementation. This can be related to the analyses of data from on-line Department of Education data sources such as Enhanced Basic Education Information System which has been the preliminary step. Based on the experience of all school heads in the district, the situational analyses start through encoding the narrative data in the computers and laptop. Then, the template on school improvement plan and annual implementation plan are usually done through computer. Then, the presentation of plans for critiquing and finalization shall be computer-assisted also for easy editing. If the plan has been prepared, the printing shall be done through printers which is another information technology device.

Another aspect of the school operation that urgently needs information and communication technology is the fiscal management system. As observed in some of the school heads, they handle financial statement manually- there is no computerize system to help them cope with their work and save time and human energy. Their work regarding managing the school budget could be enhanced by applying for example spreadsheets.

Records showing the costs involved in running a school shall be kept up to date in a thoroughly accurate manner. ICT equipment can be tremendously helpful in maintaining financial records. The electronic spreadsheet software is very useful for administrators in recording and analyzing the financial data of the educational institutions. It was found that a computer system compared to a manual system produces more accurate student, personnel and financial records (Tinio, 2013).

School administrators need to understand the capacities of the new technologies to have a personal proficiency in their use and be able to promote a school culture which encourages exploration of new techniques in teaching, learning and management (Schiller, 2003). The school heads in Trento are seemingly very active in doing their jobs. However, the system on how to do it with the aid of technology can improve the efficiency.

Based on DepEd's National Competency-Based Standards for School Heads (2010), there are management systems that needs to be organized by the school heads. First is the Enhanced Basic Education Information System and Performance Indicators that serve as on-line system for data gathering at the grassroots level. Another system is the Learner Information System or Student Tracking Systems that stores pupils' information and profile on-line. The school also need to have an annual School Report Cards (SRC) and State of the School Address that is used to communicate the status of the school in general through various data. In recording system of teacher profile, the school head needs to organize Personnel Information System.

To keep track of personnel performance, the school has to organize the Performance Appraisal System for Teachers and School Heads. To identify the training needs and capability building activities of both teachers and school head, the National Competency-Based Teaching and School Heads Standards-Teachers Strengths and Needs Assessment, Individual Plan for Professional Development and School Plan for Professional Development shall be organized. To keep track of school logistics, the school heads should organize Physical Facilities management information system (Inventory Reports on Physical Facilities, Equipment, Furniture & References).

To strengthen the framework of decentralization, the school head spearhead the School-Based Management Philippine Accreditation System for Basic Education. The school head has to accomplish Monthly Reports (Accomplishment Reports, Form 3, Form 2B). The school head presents the afore-mentioned reports and data using the appropriate technology such as computer-generated hard copies, multi-media devices (PowerPoint), laptops or desktop computers to stakeholders, DepEd Officials & Teachers.

Financial Management information system (simplified accounting and record keeping) is another school heads task. Legislation and control Management Information System (organized memoranda, orders, policies and laws from national to school level) is another system that needs to be organized. In relation to teaching and learning, curriculum Management Information System (data bank on

curriculum guides, teacher's guide, LM's and references) has to be strengthened.

Research, evaluation and guidance Management Information System is another task with great impact to academic performance. To strengthen support from stakeholders, the community Management Information System has to be organized. (Deligro,2014) stated that if these systems are performed with the effective use of appropriate technology, these will likely contribute to instilling stability and transparency in the school.

Lastly, ICT competence in operationalization is the new trend in this century-first school administrators. The day curbs the digital divide that is present in the world today (Kabithra, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlation research design. The descriptive-correlational research design aims to provide static pictures of situations as well as establish the relationship between different variables (Mcburney & White).

Furthermore, the descriptive-correlational method is one in which there is a relationship between variables and data, and a group of people or items was studied by collecting and analyzing data. In other words, only a part of the population has been studied, and findings from this were expected to be generalized to the entire population in this regard.

Respondents

The participants of the study were the 150 teachers from the schools of Trento Municipality for School Year 2023-2024. From a total teacher population of 258, the sample size is set at 150. In determining the number of teacher-respondents from each identified school, the simple random sampling technique will be used. To select the actual respondents from each school, a simple random sampling through lottery will be done.

Instruments

This study utilized an adopted questionnaire for the its independent variable. Specifically, questionnaire from 'Principals' Application of Instructional Leadership Practices for Secondary School Effectiveness in Oyo State' (Chiedozi & Victor) was used for the indicators 'instructional supervision practices' and 'time management practices,' while 'School Heads' Competence in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Management of Elementary Schools: Basis for an Intervention Plan (2016) for 'ICT Competence in Operationalization.'

The following interpretation scales was used to determine the instructional leadership practices of school administrators of Trento District .

Rating	Interval	Descriptive Interpretation	Descriptive Meaning
4	3.50-5.00	Very competent	Instructional leadership practices is oftentimes manifested.
3	2.50-3.40	Competent	Instructional leadership practices is sometimes manifested.
2	1.50-2.40	Somewhat competent	Instructional leadership practices is seldom manifested.
1	1.00-1.40	Not competent	Instructional leadership practices is never manifested.

For complementation of data, both categories of respondents, the teachers and school administrators, answered the questionnaire for the independent variable. The variable 'performance of teachers' was measured using the rating of teacher-respondents of their IPCRF (Individual Performance Commitment Review Form)

Validation of Instrument

Five experts in the field validated the adopted research questionnaire to ensure the appropriateness of the items contained in the questionnaire. Following the validation, the questionnaire was pilot-tested to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument. The questionnaire was pilot tested to a group of 10 teachers from another school from another district not be included in the study.

Procedure

The researcher followed the steps below in the gathering of data.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher observed proper protocol by asking permission and approval to conduct the study. Endorsement letters was requested from the Dean of the Graduate School of Assumption College of Nabunturan. The researcher hand carried a letter of request to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Agusan del Sur. After the positive response, a letter was sent to the Public Schools District Supervisor and likewise to the principals of selected schools in Municipality of Trento to conduct the study. In like manner, the researcher informed the teacher-respondents who were chosen to answer the survey instrument. Furthermore, the researcher observed proper ethical standards on the conduct of the study and the names of the teacher-respondents

were not indicated and any important matters were kept with utmost confidentiality.

Administration of the Research Instrument. The researcher administered the distribution of survey questionnaire personally for about three days considering the distance of the schools and ensured that respondents are well oriented as to the purpose of the study.

Retrieval of Survey Questionnaires. After a week, the retrieval of the research instrument followed with the help of the Administrative Officers then all responses were encoded by the researcher personally in Microsoft Excel.

Data Analysis

The data in this study was organized and classified based on the research design and the problems. The data were tallied and tabulated to facilitate the presentation and interpretation of the results. Statistical techniques helped the researcher in determining the validity and reliability of their research instrument. The researcher applied the following:

Mean. This refers to the mean or average that was used to derived the central tendency of the data in question. This would be used to determine the level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators in Trento District III.

Pearson r. This refers to the test statistics that would measure the statistical relationship, or association, between two continuous variables. In this study, it was used to analyze the null hypothesis and to explain the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Results and Discussion

Level of Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators

This section presented the results to the school administrators' instructional leadership practices as to supervision, time management and information and communication technology competence in operationalization.

Level of Instructional Leadership Practices as to Supervision. Table 2 revealed the results of the level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators as to supervision.

Table 2. *Instructional Leadership Practices as to Supervision*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Quality Index</i>
1. monitors teachers' instructional delivery to render suggestions for enhancement	3.7	Very Competent
2. reviews teachers' lesson notes to provide assistance for improvement	3.7	Very Competent
3. updates teachers' school attendance to ensure regular instructional delivery	3.8	Very Competent
4. provides feedback on teachers' record of work done to monitor their progress	3.7	Very Competent
5. observes teachers' truancy level to foster their dedication to their duties	3.7	Very Competent
6. oversees on teachers' participation in school meeting & conferences	3.8	Very Competent
7. monitors teachers' compliance to school scheduled programs & projects	3.7	Very Competent
8. controls on teachers' participation in school extra-curricular activities	3.6	Very Competent
Weighted Mean	3.7	Very Competent

Table 2 presented the level of Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators in terms of Supervision. It shown in the table that there two indicators placed first in rank the 'checking of staff school attendance to ensure regular instructional delivery' and 'and 'monitoring of staff participation in school meeting' got the highest mean of 3.8 with the descriptive rating of very competent. Then, followed by five indicators placed second in rank these are 'monitoring of teachers' instructional delivery to render suggestions for enhancement, checking of teachers' lesson notes to provide assistance for improvement, checking of teachers' record of work done to monitor their progress, monitoring staff truancy level to foster their dedication to their duties and monitoring of staff participation in school extra-curricular activities' with the mean of 3.6 and has a descriptive rating of very competent. 'Monitoring of staff participation in school extra-curricular activities' placed third in rank with the mean of 3.6 and the descriptive rating is very competent.

This instructional leadership practices of school administrators focusing on supervision got an overall weighted mean of 3.7 with a descriptive rating of very competent. Result manifested that the ILP of school heads of Trento Municipality as to supervision was excellent. Thus, their efficiency would not only help the teachers identify their own areas of improvement and set goals for professional development and growth but it will also give positive impact on student engagement and achievement. Sometimes supervision is misinterpreted in the field without realizing that this practice would provide valuable feedback on teaching techniques, content delivery, and classroom management. Being mindful that this process helps teachers refine their skills and adapt their methods to better meet the needs of their students.

Level of Instructional Leadership Practices as to Time Management. Table 3 presented the results of the level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators as to time management.

This Table 3 presented the level of Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators in terms of Time Management. There were eight indicators of this school administrators' ILP. Indicator 1, 'providing timely information for teachers to enhance their teaching roles' got the highest mean of 3.7 with its descriptive rating very competent. Indicator 2, 'ensuring appropriate delegation of

instructional tasks to teachers for timely delivery’ has a mean of 3.6 with its corresponding descriptive rating of very competent. Also, Indicator 3, about ‘linking school priorities with educational objectives for school effectiveness’ got the mean of 3.6 with its quality index of very competent. However, Indicator 4, ‘avoidance of procrastination in preparing the school time-table’, Indicator 5, ‘ensuring accurate allocation of time for each subject for adequate coverage of all subjects’, and indicator 6, ‘limiting the intrusion of extra-curricular activities on instructional time’ got the same mean of 3.5 with its corresponding descriptive rating of very competent. Lastly, indicator 7, ‘discouraging unnecessary and unscheduled visitors during school hours for steady instructional delivery’ and indicator 8, ‘controlling various school activities to maintain focus on instructional tasks’ both received the mean of 3.6 with the descriptive rating of very competent.

Table 3. Instructional Leadership Practices as to Time Management

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Quality Index</i>
1. provides timely information for teachers to enhance their teaching roles	3.7	Very Competent
2. ensures appropriate delegation of instructional tasks to teachers for timely delivery	3.6	Very Competent
3. links school priorities with educational objectives for school effectiveness	3.6	Very Competent
4. avoids procrastination in preparing the school time-table	3.5	Very Competent
5. ensures accurate allocation of time for each subject during observation	3.5	Very Competent
6. limits the intrusion of extra-curricular activities on instructional time	3.5	Very Competent
7. discourages unnecessary and unscheduled visitors during school hours for steady instructional delivery	3.6	Very Competent
8. controls various school activities to maintain focus on instructional tasks	3.6	Very Competent
Weighted Mean	3.6	Very Competent

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators in terms of Time Management got an overall weighted mean of 3.6 with a descriptive rating of very competent which indicates that they are well-organized. With that excellent performance in time management, occurrence of a smooth and easy school operation will be experienced by both the internal and external stakeholders. Aside from avoiding oneself from stress due to administrative tasks and functions it will also help them accomplish the administrators’ responsibilities efficiently.

Level of Instructional Leadership Practices as to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competence in Operationalization. Table 4 presents the results of the level of instructional leadership practices of school administrators as to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competence in Operationalization.

Table 4. Instructional Leadership Practices as to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competence in Operationalization

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Quality Index</i>
1. submits School Report Cards (SRC)	3.7	Very Competent
2. updates Personnel Information System (Profile)	3.7	Very Competent
3. evaluates Performance Indicators	3.5	Very Competent
4. consolidates Physical Facilities Management Information System (Inventory Reports on Physical Facilities, Equipment, Furniture and References)	3.5	Very Competent
5. submits Monthly Reports (accomplishment reports, Form 3, Form 2B)	3.5	Very Competent
6. presents the afore-mentioned reports and data using the appropriate technology such as computer-generated hard copies, multi-media devices (PowerPoint), laptops or desktop computers to stakeholders, DepEd Officials & Teachers	3.5	Very Competent
7. classifies financial management information system (simplified accounting and record keeping)	3.4	Competent
8. reviews curriculum management information system (data bank on curriculum guides, teachers’ guide, LMs and references)	3.2	Competent
Weighted Mean	3.5	Very Competent

The Table 4 shown the level of Instructional Leadership Practices of School Administrators as to Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competence in Operationalization. There are eight indicators in this ILP of school administrators. Indicator 1, ‘perform the School Report Cards (SRC) and indicator 2, ‘perform the Personnel Information System (Profile)’, both got the highest mean of 3.7 with the descriptive rating of very competent. Then, indicator 3, ‘perform the performance Indicators, indicator 4, ‘organized physical facilities management information system (Inventory Reports on Physical Facilities, Equipment, Furniture and References), indicator 5, ‘Monthly Reports (Accomplishment reports, Form 3, Form 2B) and indicator 6, ‘presents the afore-mentioned reports and data using the appropriate technology such as computer-generated hard copies, multi-media devices (PowerPoint), laptops or desktop computers to stakeholders, DepEd Officials & Teachers’ all got the mean of 3.5 and interpreted as very competent.

However, indicator 7, ‘organized financial management information system (simplified accounting and record keeping) has the mean of 3.4 with descriptive rating of competent. Then, indicator 8, ‘organized curriculum management information system (data bank on curriculum guides, teachers’ guide, LMs and references) got the lowest mean of 3.2 with the descriptive rating of competent.

Overall results revealed that the school head competence in information and communication technology in operationalization got a weighted mean of 3.5 interpreted as very competent. It can be inferred that school administrators are well-verse about the use of

information technology in schools' operation such as making of reports and organizing systems. This result indicates that the main priority of the school administrators nowadays in terms of technology use is on the generation of reports and establishments of the systems. Lastly, it is the school managers who are responsible in providing essential supplemental learning assistance to teachers and learners hence, possessing an extra skill like utilizing diverse of computer gadgets, application and other products of technology are very significant specially in administering the school.

Level of Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) Ratings of Teachers. Reflected in Table 5 is the summary on the level of Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF).

Table 5. *Level of Performance of Teachers Individual Performance Commitment Review Forms (IPCRF)*

<i>No. of Teacher</i>	<i>Mean Rating of IPCRF</i>	<i>Quality Index</i>
150	4.5	Outstanding

The Table 5 showed that the level of performance of 150 teacher-respondents based on their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) rating obtained an overall mean score of 4.5 with the adjectival rating of outstanding. An indicative proving the efficiency of individuals in performing the mandated tasks with a high level of confidence and behavior of employees. This performance represents an extraordinary level of achievement and commitment in terms of quality and time, technical skills and knowledge, ingenuity, creativity and initiative. Employees at this performance level should have demonstrated exceptional job mastery in all areas of responsibility. Employee achievement and contributions to the organizations are of marked excellence.

Significant Relationship Between the Instructional Leadership Practices of School Heads and to the Performance of Teachers.

The Table 6 presented the Results Correlation between the Instructional Leadership Practices of the school heads and Teachers Performance.

Table 6. *Results Correlation*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Correlation Coeff.</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. Instructional Leadership Practices	0.185	0.109	No Significant
2. Individual Performance Commitment Review Form			

The table showed that there is no significant relationship between instructional leadership practices of school heads and performance rating of teachers with the p-value of 0.185. The result revealed that the p-value of 0.185 is greater than 0.05 which means that deviation from the null hypothesis is not statistically significant and the null hypothesis is accepted. Interpretation revealed that the instructional leadership practices of school managers conform to the performance of the teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, instructional leadership practices as to supervision, time management and information and communication technology competence in operationalization has no relatively association between the teachers' performance. It indicates that teachers performed their duties and responsibilities as an educator according to their commitment and dedication. With that profound accountability being an educationalist, whose passion is to potentially produce holistic individuals, the absence of instructional leadership practices would not be an obstruction towards teachers' highly proficient performance. Furthermore, Mustafa & Othman have found that there can be a clear connection between efficiency and teachers' work performance. They noted that teachers showed better performance if the intensity of commitment is better. Thus, when teachers are incredibly motivated, the success of their work becomes significant.

Additionally, teachers are inspired by a teacher-centered approach to educational management. Teacher-centered operational leadership style is distinguished by greater engagement in decision-making; reduced tight monitoring of teachers; never-ending directorial sustenance for teacher development; good social relationships; and open interactions. This philosophy is only achievable when the school heads as school administrators, beyond or above their management positions, strive to meet as many specific preferences as necessary and guide teachers with extreme respect and a great mindset and involvement in their wellbeing. Led by this principle, the school heads establish a working relationship that is characterized by a strong culture of harmony,

On the other hand, to become efficient and effective school administrators, school heads must perform five outstanding leadership practices (Kouzes & Posner)

that provide the foundation for organizational performance by suggesting what attitudes and behaviors school officials need to accomplish to become successful leaders. These include: Modeling the way (creating expectations of success and providing a precedent for everyone to follow); Inspiring a shared vision (coming up with new ideas and generating an ideal and distinctive picture of what an organization should become); Challenging the process (looking at challenges as tools for learning); Enabling others to act (fostering cooperation, establishing trust, and generating momentum); and Encouraging the heart (creating and maintaining elevated expectations, keeping the people committed to them by preserving the connection between incentives and performance). Driven by these abilities, a school head is likely to succeed.

As emphasized by the researchers Cherry Joy C. Aquino, Bonimar T. Afalla, and Fitzgerald L. Fabelico in their study on Managing Educational Institutions: School heads' Leadership Practices and Teachers' Performance of New Viscaya State University Philippines, that there are no significant relationships between the quality of leadership skills implemented by school heads and the success of teachers.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are strongly advocated:

The Department of Education supports enhancement seminar workshop to improve school head instructional leadership practices as to supervision, time management and Information and Communication Technology Competence in Operationalization.

The School Leaders/ Public Schools District Supervisor regularly monitor school administrators' performance in managing the schools to become competent leaders as to supervision, time management, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Operationalization.

School Administrators immerse themselves in different trainings to improve their technological skills as they manage and operate their respective assigned schools.

The teachers should be receptive to take opportunities and be willing to undergo basic and advance orientation and training to empower them with a mission to boost their instructional performance

The teachers must be respected in school to effective development in terms of instructional academic and administrative task.

School managers and teachers must participate a reorientation DepEd Policy and Guidelines for personal, moral and professional growth

References

Ampofo, Ghana Samuel Yaw , , Ghana George Adino, Kenya Martin Ogola (2019) IAFOR Journal of Education Volume 7 – Issue 2 –Influence of School Heads' Direct Supervision on Teacher Role Performance in Public Senior High Schools, Central Region, University of Cape Coast Onyango Kenyatta University, Kenyatta University, Kenya

Archibong, Florence Imaobong , Instructional Supervision In The Administration Of Secondary Education: A Panacea For Quality Assurance Faculty Of Education University Of Port Harcourt Nigeria

Aquino, Cherry Joy C., Afalla, Bonimar T. Afalla, Fabelico, Fitzgerald L. (2021) Managing educational institutions: School heads' leadership practices and teachers' performance Department of Education, Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines College of Teacher Education, Nueva Vizcaya State University, Philippines

Caballes, Dennis G. (February 2021) School Heads Competence and Qualifications: It's Influence on the School Performance, Centro Escolar University & Lilia Peregrino Narra National High School , CiiT International Journal of Data Mining and Knowledge Engineering, Vol 13, No 1

Cadag, Christopher E. (2024) The Effectiveness of Individual Performance Commitment Review Form as an Evaluation Tool to Improve Teachers' Performance: Basis for Technical Assistance chriscadag.biggs@gmail.com School of Graduate Studies, St. Louise de Marillac College of Sorsogon, Sorsogon City, Philippines

Chiedozi, O. L. & Victor, A. K. (2017). Principals' application of instructional leadership practices for secondary school effectiveness in Oyo State. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Education*, Jonaed, Volume 13, NO. 1 MAY 2017

Damasco, Bernabe E (March 2016) School Heads' Competence in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Management of Elementary Schools: Basis for an Intervention Plan

Dangara, Yunusa (2015) *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.6, No.10, The Impact of Instructional Supervision on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Nasarawa State, Nigeria Usman Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC), RS4.35 Nassarawa Eggon Unit Command, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Delas Penas, Jose D. Supervisory Competencies of School Heads in Relation to

Teachers' Performance <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1969-2970> josedelaspenas@gmail.com Jose Rizal Memorial State University-Tampilisan Campus Zamboanga Del Norte, Philippines

Dometita, Jophel E & Benavides, Noel G. (2023) Profile of School Heads and their

Fevre, Deirdre Le (July 29, 2023) THE EDUCATION HUB University of Auckland, New Zealand. Education consultant in New Zealand, Australia and Sweden.

Gonzalez, Jennifer (2015) Goal-Setting for Teachers: 8 Paths to Self- Improvement

Hallinger, P. and Murphy, J. (1985) Assessing the Instructional Management Behavior of Principals. The Elementary School

Journal, 86, 217-247. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/461445>

Khan, Iqbal Amin & Umar Ali Khan, Dera Ismail Khan ,Syed Munir Ahmad, Muhammad

Naseer-ud-Din (2015) FWU Journal of Social Sciences, Vol.9, No.2, 82-94 The Effect of Training on Principals' Time Management Practices: A Focus on Time Management Areas, School's Level, Locality and Complexity Institute of Education & Research, Gomal University, Institute of Education & Research, University of Peshawar Institute of Education & Research, Kohat University of Science & Technology

Michlalah, Jeffrey Glanz (2018) Journal of Educational Supervision Chronicling Perspectives about the State of Instructional Supervision by Eight Prominent Scholars of Supervision ,Jerusalem College, Israel, yosglanz@gmail.com

Murry, John Time Management Tips for School Leaders Colorado Christian's Master of Education in Educational Leadership Program

McBurney, D. & White, T. (2009). Research Methods. New York, NY: CengageLearning.

McBrayer, Juliann Sergi 4785659; Akins, Carter; Gutierrez de Blume, Antonio; Cleveland, Richard; and Pannell, Summer (2020) (July 28,2023) "Instructional Leadership Practices and School Leaders' Self-Efficacy," School Leadership Review:Vol.15:Iss.1,Article13.Availableat:<https://scholarworks.sfasu.edu/slr/vol15/iss1/13>

Pitpit, G. M. (2020). Elementary school principals' instructional leadership practices to retain novice teachers in the Philippines. Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies. Walden University. Elementary School Principals' Instructional Leadership Practices to Retain Novice Teachers in the Philippines (waldenu.edu)

Silay, Nur (May 2022) Educational Administrators' Time Management akademik Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi, Yıl: 10, Sayı: 128, s. 80-89 ISSN: 2148-2489 Doi Number: <http://dx.doi.org/10.29228/ASOS.57989> Yayın Geliş Tarihi / Article Arrival Date Yayımlanma Tarihi / Fatih Sultan Mehmet Vakıf Üniversitesi, Temel.Egitimnsilay@fsm.edu.tr Orcid: 0000-0002-1360-130210(128):80-89 DOI: 10.29228/ASOS.57989

Tulod, Ryan G. & Naparan , Genesis B. Naparan (2021) Time Management Strategies of School Administrators Towards Effective Administration : A Phenomenological Study DOI: 10.15804

Opena, Estrelle Rose A. (July 2022) Integration Of Information Communication

Technology (Ict) In The New Normal Learning: Its Effect On Teachers' Individual Performance Commitment Rating Home Vol. 9 Issue. 7 EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management Graduate Student, Davao del Norte State College DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra10784>

Victor, Akinfolarin Akinwale & Chiedozi, Onyali Loyce P. (July 28, 2023)Principals' Application of Instructional Leadership Practices for Secondary School Effectiveness in Oyo State ,Department of Educational Management and Policy, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria.

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